

EVALUATION ON RESSION BEHAVIORS OF B₄C CONTAINING POROUS CARBON MATERIAL AS AN ADVANCED THERMAL PROTECTION SYSTEM

Tatsuki Koshikawa¹, Yutaro Arai¹ and Yasuo Kogo¹

¹Department of Materials Science and Technology, Tokyo University of Science, 6-3-1, Niijuku, Katsushika-ku, Tokyo, Japan 10.1007/s10853-021-05950-x
Email : 8224528@ed.tus.ac.jp, Web Page : <https://www.tus.ac.jp>

Keywords: Resins, Thermal properties, High temperature properties, Foams, Environmental degradation

ABSTRACT

The ablative thermal protection system (Ablator) can protect re-entry vehicles from severe aerodynamic heating during re-entry. Ablators are carbon-based materials with impregnated resin, and the decomposition of resin during re-entry prevents the temperature increase for components. Carbon monolith has been further developed as a porous carbon substrate, and it has been found that there is no significant difference in recession behaviors of carbon monoliths with or without resin. In addition, it shows superior recession behaviors to conventional porous carbons. A carbon monolith is prepared by carbonizing a porous phenolic resin (phenolic monolith) with the same structure as a carbon monolith. Since phenolic monolith is fabricated by using polymerization-induced phase separation (PIPS), it makes the addition of a second phase and the design of the structure possible. In this study, a B₄C particle dispersed carbon monolith (BCM) is prepared. The mechanical properties of them are evaluated by compression testing. The result shows mechanical properties of BCM are similar to conventional porous carbon despite the addition of a second phase. Ablation behavior is evaluated by an arc-wind tunnel test simulated for a re-entry environment. The result shows internal temperature is decreased.

1 INTRODUCTION

Ablators are well-known as one of the thermal protection systems (TPS) for re-entry vehicles and composed of carbon fibers and resin. Since the decomposition of resin (an endothermic reaction) prevents the increase of temperature for the vehicles, they protect the vehicles from aerodynamic heating during re-entry [1]. A typical example of an ablator is phenol-impregnated carbon ablator (PICA). PICA has been applied to vehicles in the Stardust mission, and the advanced version "PICA-X" has been used for the heatshield of the Space X Dragon spacecraft [2]. A notable feature of PICA is light weight because it composed of carbon felt and phenolic resin. However, it has been reported that PICA exhibits severe mechanical erosion [3].

Therefore, we have proposed to apply three-dimensional networked porous carbon (TNPC) as the substrate and prepare a porous carbon-based ablator (PCA) by impregnating TNPC with resin [4]. As a TNPC, carbon monolith has been developed and prepared by carbonizing a porous phenolic resin (phenolic monolith) with the same structure as a carbon monolith. The evaluation on carbon monolith has revealed that the carbon monolith has superior mechanical properties compared to PICA and the recession behavior has been improved by the suppression of mechanical erosion compared to PICA [5].

Since a phenolic monolith is fabricated using polymerization-induced phase separation (PIPS), the introduction of a second phase and the design of the structure are possible. A carbon monolith dispersed with ZrO₂ (ZCM) has been successfully prepared in previous studies. As the second phase, ZrO₂ was chosen owing to its low thermal conductivity (~ 2.5 W/m · K) and high melting point (2680 °C). It has revealed that the addition of ZrO₂ improves the recession behavior of carbon monolith and the amount of recession decreases compared to PCA. The result suggests ZCM can be applied to TPS without impregnation of resin [6]. On the other hand, the high density of ZrO₂ (~ 6 g/cm³) causes the increase in weight and it makes the application to aerospace component difficult.

In response to this challenge, we have selected boron carbide (B_4C) as an alternative secondary phase. B_4C is notable for its high hardness (ranging between 38 and 44 GPa), a high melting point (2450 °C), and a lower density (around 2.45 g/cm³) [7]. It is expected that B_4C acts as a barrier to the recession. By the oxidation of B_4C , B_2O_3 is formed and the evaporation of B_2O_3 is an endothermic process ($\Delta H = 322$ KJ/mol, at 1250°C, 0.027 atm) and it prevents the increase of temperature for components [8]. B_4C containing carbon monolith is also expected as a candidate of advanced ablator without impregnation of resin and it will protect from severe aerodynamic heating during re-entry by the phase change of B_2O_3 . Thus, we have defined this novel TPS as a "phase change shield system" (PCSS), distinguishing it from conventional ablators. The objective of this study is to develop a material process for B_4C dispersed carbon monolith (BCM) as a PCSS and evaluate the relationship between particle content, mechanical properties, thermal properties, and recession behavior under simulated re-entry conditions.

2 Experimental procedures

2.1 Fabrication of BCM

As the precursor of carbon monolith, a phenolic monolith was prepared. Then, the monomer concentration (ω , wt%) was defined as the ratio of resin and curing agent to solution by the following equation:

$$\omega = \frac{W_{resin} + W_{cure}}{W_{solution}} \quad (1)$$

$$W_{solution} = W_{resin} + W_{cure} + W_{solvent} \quad (2)$$

W_{resin} , W_{cure} , $W_{solution}$ and $W_{solvent}$ were the weight of phenolic resin, curing agent, solution, and solvent, respectively. A resol-type phenolic resin (PL2407 by Gunei Chemical, Japan), concentrated sulfuric acid, and ethylene glycol were used as resin, curing agent and solvent. These were mixed in a weight ratio of 13:1:21 (hereafter as the mixed solution) in a beaker. B_4C particles (BBI10PB, particle size: 500 nm, Kojundo Chemical Laboratory Co., Ltd, Japan) were used as the particles. The mixed solution was held at 40°C in an ambient atmosphere for 12 h to cure by using an oven (DRN320DE, ADVANTEC TOYO KAISHA, LTD. Japan). After 4 h from the beginning of curing, B_4C particles were added by 3.1, 6.1, or 9.2 vol% to mixed solution. The solution was stirred and held under a reduced pressure of about -0.08 MPa for 30 minutes using a rotary pump to remove air bubbles. After 12 h, the temperature was increased to 180°C and held for 2 h. After that, samples were cooled to room temperature (25°C) over ~12 h. After curing, the solvent in the samples were removed in water at 80°C for 72 h and dried in the oven at 80°C for 72 h to obtain the B_4C dispersed phenolic monolith (hereafter denoted as BPM). BPM was carbonized at 950°C for ~4 h in an atmospheric furnace (FT-POT-300, Fulltech) under an Ar atmosphere to obtain the B_4C particle dispersed carbon monolith (hereafter denoted as BCM). BCM with B_4C particles by 3.1, 6.1, and 9.2 vol% were defined as 3.1 BCM, 6.1 BCM and 9.2 BCM, respectively.

2.2 Basic characterization of structures for 9.2 BCM

9.2 BCM was cut into five layers as shown in Figure 1. The bottom of the beaker used during fabrication was defined as the XY plane, and the center of the XY plane in the third layer along the Z-axis was observed by scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Furthermore, the density of each layer was measured to evaluate the dispersion of particles.

2.3 Evaluation of mechanical properties for BCM

BCM was cut into rectangular blocks with size of 10×10×20 mm and 8×8×30 mm. The latter shaped continuously into a dumbbell with a cross-section of 5×8 mm in the center. The shapes of both compression test specimens are shown in Figure 2. Compression tests were conducted using a universal testing machine (model 5967, INSTRON, The U. S.), with a crosshead speed of 0.1 mm/min. The load was recorded using a 30 kN load cell, and displacement was measured using an extensometer attached to the compression jig. From these values, the Young's modulus and compression strength were evaluated.

Figure 1. A schematic diagram of 9.2BCM

Figure 2. Shape of compression specimens

2.4 Arc-wind tunnel test

Arc-wind tunnel tests were conducted to evaluate the ablation behaviors of BCM. The tests used a 1 MW class arc heater at Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency/Institute of Space and Astronautical Science (JAXA/ISAS) in their arc-wind tunnel. In the tests, the high-enthalpy flow heated by arc heater is emitted from the nozzle into the chamber, allowing for simulated testing of atmospheric re-entry conditions. The appearance of the test specimens before and during the test in the arc heating wind tunnel were shown in Figure 3. By varying the distance between the air nozzle and the test specimen, the heat flux and dynamic pressure at stagnation point were adjusted. The size of specimens and specimen holder were exhibited in Figure 4. The specimen surface was $\Phi 50$ mm and set to bakelite holder. Nozzle distances were set at 150 mm, 100 mm, or 80 mm. The specimen surface was exposed for 30s by high enthalpy flow. The surface temperature was measured during heating by using radiation thermometer (emissivity $\varepsilon = 0.90$). The internal temperature was measured during heating and until 20 min after heating. Internal temperature was measured by inserting a type K thermocouple at 20 mm and 30 mm depth from the surface. After arc-wind tunnel test, the recession length of surface was measured by using a laser displacement sensor (LK-G155, KEYENCE CORPORATION, Japan).

Figure 3. A typical appearance of the specimen: (a)Before test, (b)During test

Table 1. Test conditions

Test	Specimen	Nozzle distance (mm)	Exposure time (s)	Emissivity	Heat flux (MW/m ²)	Dynamic pressure (kPa)
A	3.1 BCM	150			1.92	3.09
	6.1 BCM					
	9.2 BCM					
B	3.1 BCM	100	30	0.90	3.54	10.10
	6.1 BCM					
	9.2 BCM					
C	3.1 BCM	80			6.18	20.11
	6.1 BCM					
	9.2 BCM					

Figure 4. Cross section of arc wind tunnel specimen

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Density of 9.2BCM

The relationship between normalized length (z) and density of 9.2 BCM and carbon monolith is shown in Figure 5. The addition of B₄C increases the density of each layer in the 9.2 BCM compared with that of the carbon monolith. Furthermore, because the relationship between normalized length (z) and density is similar for both the 9.2 BCM and the carbon monolith, the B₄C particles in the BCM are considered uniformly dispersed.

Figure 5. Relationship between normalized length (z) and density

3.2 Structural Observation

Microstructures of 9.2 BCM were presented in Figure 6. The monolith structure, which is a typical microstructure of monolith [5], is maintained even with the addition of B₄C particles. Agglomerates of B₄C approximately 2.0–3.0 μm in size were observed. However, because the monolithic structure was preserved, it was confirmed that the ZCM fabrication process can be applied to BCM.

Figure 6. Typical microstructures of 9.2 BCM

3.3 Evaluation on Mechanical Properties

Young's modulus of carbon monolith, 3.1 BCM, 6.1 BCM, 9.2 BCM is 7, 3.8, 1.8 and 1.6 GPa, respectively. In addition, the compressive strength of carbon monolith, 3.1 BCM, 6.1 BCM, 9.2 BCM is ~ 110 , ~ 60 , ~ 30 and ~ 25 MPa, respectively. These results show the compression strength and Young's modulus decrease with increase of the B_4C particles. This suggests that agglomerates influence the mechanical properties in different ways. On the other hand, the compressive strength of a conventional TNPC is ~ 25 MPa [9] and it clearly indicates carbon monolith can maintain a certain level of compressive strength even after the addition of B_4C particles.

3.4 Arc Heating Wind Tunnel Test

The relationship between surface temperature and heat flux during tests is shown in Figure 7. In tests A and B, the carbon monolith showed a lower surface temperature than the BCM, whereas in test C this relationship was reversed. This reversal is attributed to the surface temperature in test C exceeding the melting point of B_4C , thereby causing reactions different from those occurring in tests A and B.

Figure 7. Temperature history of surface temperature (BCM and Carbon Monolith) [5]

The relationship between internal temperature and heat flux during tests is shown in Figure 8. At that time, the internal temperature of carbon monolith in test B could not be measured accurately because the specimen fractured. The BCM shows a lower internal temperature than the carbon monolith at every test. Moreover, the internal temperature decreases as the B_4C content increases. This can be attributed to the specific heat capacity of B_4C ($1.84 \text{ J/g} \cdot \text{K}$) and evaporation of B_2O_3 , which is evolved by the oxidation of B_4C . The B_4C particles within the specimen absorbed heat as their temperature rose, thereby suppressing the overall temperature increase.

Figure 8. Temperature history of internal temperature (BCM and Carbon Monolith) [5]

4 Conclusion

BCM was fabricated by carbonizing a phenolic monolith with B₄C particles. Despite B₄C agglomerates (2–3 μm), the monolith structure was maintained. Compression tests showed that the strength decreases with the increase of B₄C content. Arc wind tunnel tests revealed lower internal temperatures for BCM than for the carbon monolith at all conditions. It was attributed to high specific heat (1.84 J / g · K) of B₄C and the evaporation B₂O₃. Thus, PCSS (in this study BCM) preserves the mechanical properties of the base monolith while providing superior thermal protection, making it a strong candidate for TPS in high-heat-flux environments.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The results of this study were derived from the arc wind tunnel tests conducted at the Institute of Space and Astronautical Science, Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency (ISAS/JAXA). The authors are grateful to Tetsuo Yoshida and Shogo Sakamoto for their assistance with these tests.

REFERENCES

- [1] Sylvia M. Johnson, Thermal Protection Materials and Systems : An Overview, *Engineered Ceramics Advanced Ceramics and Ceramic Matrix Composites*, 2016, pp. 224-244
- [2] Obinna Uyanna and Hamidreza Najafi, Thermal protection systems for space vehicles: A review on technology development, current challenges and future prospects, *Acta Astronautica*, **176**, 2020, pp. 341-356
- [3] Jean Lachaud, Nagi Mansour, Alejandro Ceballos, Dusan Pejakovic, Luning Zhang and Jochen Marschall, Validation of a volume-averaged fiber-scale model for the oxidation of carbon-fiber preform, *42nd AIAA Thermophysics Conference*, 27-30 June 2011, Honolulu, Hawaii
- [4] Yuki Kubota, Toshiki Fujita, Yusei Kaneda, Ryo Inoue and Yasuo Kogo, Thermal Protection Performance of Porous Carbon Ablators with Three Different Matrices, *Journal of Spacecraft and Rockets*, **55**, 2018, pp. 1222-1229
- [5] Rina Ono, Kenjiro Tsukamoto, Yutaro Arai and Yasuo Kogo, Experimental and analytical evaluation of an aerospace thermal protection system: Carbon monolith ablator, *MRS Advances*, **9**, 2024, pp. 822-829
- [6] Hiroya Taniguchi, Yutaro Arai and Yasuo Kogo, Evaluation on ablation behavior of ZrO₂ nanoparticle-dispersed porous carbon composites, *Proceedings of the 21st European Conference on Composite Materials Volume 2 – Material Science*, 2024, pp. 441-448
- [7] The Chemical Society of Japan, Kagaku Binran (Handbook of material data), Basic Section I, 5th Revised Edition, *Maruzen Publishing*, 2004, pp. 702-703
- [8] The Chemical Society of Japan, Kagaku Binran (Handbook of material data), Basic Section II, 5th Revised Edition, *Maruzen Publishing*, 2004, pp. 251
- [9] Y. Arai, Y. Daigo, E. Kojo, R. Inoue and Y. Kogo, Relationship between the microstructures and Young's modulus of 3D-networked porous carbon material, *Journal of Materials Science*, **56**, 2021, pp. 10338-10352